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Review Article

ANALYTICAL METHOD VALIDATION: A BRIEF REVIEW**P.Lingaeswara Rao^{1*}, Ch.V.Suresh², BN Girish Kumar³, B.Jones³, B Abhishek³,
D.Rajesh³**¹Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Chennupati Indo American School of Pharmacy, Narasaraopet, Palnadu(Dt), Andhra Pradesh, pin:522601.²Principal, Department of Pharmaceutics, Chennupati Indo American School of Pharmacy, Narasaraopet, Palnadu(Dt), Andhra Pradesh, pin:522601.³Research Scholar, Department of Pharmaceutics, Chennupati Indo American School of Pharmacy, Narasaraopet, Palnadu(Dt), Andhra Pradesh, pin:522601.**Abstract:**

Method development is a broad term. In both quantitative and qualitative analysis developing a new method either for estimation of quantity of substance or to check the presence of the required component is a necessitate step. Validation means to establish the characteristics parameters of the method. It also helps by revealing the limitations and their extent of the method. Both terms are essential to create and then establish for any drug component so that it can be used in any pharmaceutical industry for its benefit. Validation is an applied approach to verify that a method is suitable to function as a quality control tool. The objective of any analytical measurement is to obtain consistent, reliable and accurate data. Validated analytical methods play a major role in achieving this goal. An analytical method consists of the techniques, method, procedure and protocol. Analytical method validation includes the determination of accuracy, precision, LOD, LOQ, linearity and range. The results from method validation can be used to moderator the quality, reliability and consistency of analytical results, which is an integral part of any good analytical practice. Validation of analytical methods is also required by most regulations and quality standards that impact laboratories. The main objective of this review article is to guide the young researchers to improve the quality of analytical method development and validation process. Generally, the guidelines are followed as laid by ICH and USP which are followed worldwide

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INTRODUCTION:

Validation of an analytical procedure is the process by which it is established, by laboratory studies, that the performance characteristics of the procedure meet the requirements for its intended use¹. All analytical methods that are intended to be used for analyzing any clinical samples will need to be validated. Validation of analytical methods is an essential but time-consuming activity for most analytical development laboratories. It is therefore important to understand the requirements of method validation in more detail and the options that are available to allow for optimal utilization of analytical resources in a development laboratory².

TYPES OF ANALYTICAL PROCEDURES TO BE VALIDATED³

The validation of analytical procedures is directed to the four most common types of analytical procedures:

- Identification tests.
- Quantitative tests for impurities' content.
- Limit tests for the control of impurities.
- Quantitative tests of the active moiety in samples of drug substance or drug product or other selected component(s) in the drug product.

ICH/USP Validation Requirements & Parameters

USP	ICH
Specificity	Specificity
Linearity and Range	Linearity
Accuracy	Range
Precision	Accuracy
Limit of Detection	Precision Repeatability Intermediate Precision Reproducibility
Limit of Quantitation	Limit of Detection
Ruggedness	Limit of Quantitation
Robustness	

1.Accuracy: The International Convention on Harmonization (ICH) defines the accuracy of an analytical procedure as the closeness of agreement between the values that are accepted either as conventional true values or an accepted reference value and the value found.

For drug substance, accuracy may be defined by the application of the analytical procedure to an analyte of known purity (e.g., a reference standard).

For the drug product, accuracy will be determined by application of the analytical procedure to synthetic mixtures of the drug product components to which known amounts of analyte have been added within the range of the procedure.

Accuracy is usually reported as percent recovery by the assay (using the proposed analytical procedure) of known added amount of analyte in the sample or as the difference between the mean and the accepted true value together with the confidence intervals. The range for the accuracy limit should be within the linear range. Typical accuracy of the recovery of the drug substance is expected to be about 99 –101%. Typical accuracy of the recovery of the drug product is expected to be about 98 – 102%. Values of accuracy of recovery data beyond this range need to be investigated as appropriate.

Precision:

The precision of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement (degree of scatter) between a series of measurements obtained from multiple samples of the same homogeneous sample under prescribed conditions. Precision is usually investigated at three levels: repeatability, intermediate precision, and reproducibility.

Repeatability: Repeatability is a measure of the precision under the same operating conditions over a short interval of time, that is, under normal operating conditions of the analytical method with the same equipment. It is sometimes referred to as intra - assay precision.

The ICH recommends that repeatability be assessed using a minimum of nine determinations covering the specified range for the procedure (e.g., three concentrations/three replicates as in the accuracy experiment) or using a minimum of six determinations at 100% of the test concentration. Reporting of the standard deviation, relative standard deviation (coefficient of variation), and confidence interval is required.

Intermediate Precision: Intermediate precision is defined as the variation within the same laboratory. The extent to which intermediate precision needs to be established depends on the circumstances under which the procedure is intended to be used. Typical parameters that are investigated include day - to - day

variation, analyst variation, and equipment variation. Depending on the extent of the study, the use of experimental design is encouraged. Experimental design will minimize the number of experiments that need to be performed.

Reproducibility: Reproducibility measures the precision between laboratories. This parameter is considered in the standardization of an analytical procedure. To validate this characteristic, similar studies need to be performed at different laboratories using the same homogeneous sample lot and the same experimental design. In the case of method transfer between two laboratories, different approaches may be taken to achieve the successful transfer of the procedure⁴⁻⁵.

Specificity⁶:

The ICH defines specificity as the ability to assess unequivocally an analyte in the presence of components that may be expected to be present. The specificity for an assay and impurity tests should be approached from two angles:

1. When impurities are available: The specificity of an assay method is determined by comparing test results from an analysis of sample containing the impurities, degradation products, or placebo ingredients with those obtained from an analysis of samples without the impurities, degradation products, or placebo ingredients.

2. If impurities are not available: Specificity may be demonstrated by comparing the test results of samples containing impurities or degradation products to a second well characterized procedure or other validated analytical procedure (orthogonal method). This should include samples stored under relevant stress conditions (light, heat, humidity, acid/base hydrolysis and oxidation).

Detection Limit⁷

The detection limit (DL) is a characteristic for the limit test only. It is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample that can be detected but not necessarily quantitated under the stated experimental conditions. The detection is usually expressed as the concentration of the analyte in the sample, for example, percentage, parts per million (ppm), or parts per billion (ppb).

There are several approaches to establish the detection limit. Visual evaluation may be used for non-instrumental (e.g., solution color) and instrumental methods. In this case, the detection limit is determined by the analysis of a series of samples with known concentrations and establishing the minimum level at which the analyte can be reliably detected. For

instrumental procedures that exhibit background noise, it is common to compare measured signals from samples with known low concentrations of analyte with those of the blank samples. The minimum concentration at which the analyte can reliably be detected is established using an acceptable signal - to - noise ratio of 2 : 1 or 3 : 1. Presentation of relevant chromatograms is sufficient for justification of the detection limit.

Another approach estimates the detection limit from the standard deviation of the response and the slope of the calibration curve. The standard deviation can be determined either from the standard deviation of multiple blank samples or from the standard deviation of the y intercepts of the regression lines done in the range of the detection limit.

$$DL = 3.3 \sigma / S$$

where σ is the standard deviation of the response and S is the slope of the calibration curve.

Quantitation Limit⁸

The Quantitation Limit (QL) is a characteristic of quantitative assays for low levels of compounds in sample matrices, such as impurities in bulk drug substances and degradation products in finished pharmaceuticals. Quantitation Limit is defined as the concentration of related substance in the sample that will give a signal - to - noise ratio of 10 : 1. The quantitation limit of a method is affected by both the detector sensitivity and the accuracy of sample preparation at the low concentration of the impurities. ICH recommends three approaches to the estimation of quantitation limit. The first approach is to evaluate it by visual evaluation and may be used for non-instrumental methods and instrumental methods. Quantitation Limit is determined by the analysis of samples with known concentrations of analyte and by establishing the minimum level at which the analyte can be quantitated with acceptable accuracy and precision.

The second approach determines the signal - to - noise ratio by comparing measured signals from samples with known low concentrations of analyte with those of blank samples. Quantitation Limit is the minimum concentration at which the analyte can be reliably quantified at the signal - to - noise ratio of 10 : 1. The third approach estimates quantitation limit by the equation $QL = 10 \sigma / S$. The value of σ may be estimated by (1) calculating the standard deviation of the responses obtained from the measurement of the analytical background response of an appropriate number of blank samples or (2) calculating the residual

standard deviation of the regression line from the calibration curve using samples containing the analyte in the range of the quantitation limit .

Linearity⁹

Linearity is defined as ability of the method to obtain test results which are directly proportional to the concentration of analyte in the sample within a given range. There are two general approaches for determining the linearity of the method. The first approach is to weigh different amounts of standard directly to prepare linearity solutions at different concentrations. Another approach is to prepare a stock solution of high concentration. Linearity is then demonstrated directly by dilution of the standard stock solution. Linearity is best evaluated by visual inspection of a plot of the signals as a function of analyte concentration. Subsequently, the variable data are generally used to calculate a regression line by the least - squares method. At least five concentration levels should be used. Under normal circumstances, linearity is acceptable with a coefficient of determination (r^2) of ≥ 0.997 .

Range¹⁰

The range of an analytical procedure is the interval between the upper and lower concentration of analyte in the sample for which it has been demonstrated that the analytical procedure has a suitable level of precision, accuracy, and linearity. The range is normally expressed in the same units as test results (e.g., percent, parts per million) obtained by the analytical procedure. For the assay of drug substance or finished drug product, it is normally recommended to have a range of 80 – 120% of the nominal concentration. For content uniformity, a normal range would cover 70 – 130% of the nominal concentration, unless a wider and more appropriate range (e.g., metered - dose inhalers) is justified. For dissolution testing, a normal range is $\pm 20\%$ over the specified range. If the acceptance criterion for a controlled - release product covers a region from 20% after 1 h, and up to 90% after 24 h, the validated range would be 0 – 110% of the label claim. In this case, the lowest appropriate quantifiable concentration of analyte will be used as the lowest limit as 0% is not appropriate.

Robustness¹¹

Robustness of an analytical procedure is a measure of the analytical method to remain unaffected by small but deliberate variations in method parameters and provides an indication of its reliability during normal usage. The evaluation of robustness is normally considered during the development phase and depends on the type of procedure under study. It should show

the reliability of an analysis with respect to deliberate variations in method parameters.

If measurements are susceptible to variations in analytical conditions, the analytical conditions should be suitably controlled or a precautionary statement should be included in the procedure. One consequence of the evaluation of robustness should be that a series of system suitability parameters (e.g., resolution test) is established to ensure that the validity of the analytical procedure is maintained whenever used. Examples of typical variations are: stability of analytical solutions, extraction time.

In the case of liquid chromatography, examples of typical variations are influence of variations of pH in a mobile phase, influence of variations in mobile phase composition, Different columns (different lots and/or suppliers), temperature, flow rate.

Ruggedness:¹¹ Ruggedness is the of reproducibility of the test results obtained for identical samples under normal (but variable) test conditions.

PROCESS OF ANALYTICAL METHOD VALIDATION¹²

The typical process that is followed in an analytical method validation is chronologically listed below:

1. Planning and deciding on the method validation experiments
2. Writing and approval of method validation protocol
3. Execution of the method validation protocol
4. Analysis of the method validation data
5. Reporting the analytical method validation
6. Finalizing the analytical method procedure

The validation protocol should be numbered, signed and dated, and should contain as a minimum the following information¹³:

- Objectives, scope of coverage of the validation study.
- Validation team membership, their qualifications and responsibilities.
- Type of validation: prospective, concurrent, retrospective, re-validation.
- Number and selection of batches to be on the validation study.
- A list of all equipment to be used; their normal and worst case operating parameters.
- Outcome of IQ, OQ for critical equipment.
- Requirements for calibration of all measuring devices.
- Critical process parameters and their respective tolerances.
- Description of the processing steps: copy of the master documents for the product.

- Sampling points, stages of sampling, methods of sampling, sampling plans.
- Statistical tools to be used in the analysis of data.
- Training requirements for the processing operators.
- Validated test methods to be used in in-process testing and for the finished product.
- Specifications for raw and packaging materials and test methods.
- Forms and charts to be used for documenting results.
- Format for presentation of results, documenting conclusions and for approval of study results.

Documentation¹⁴

It is essential that the validation program is documented and that the documentation is properly maintained. Approval and release of the process for use in routine manufacturing should be based upon a review of all the validation documentation, including data from the equipment qualification, process performance qualification, and product/package testing to ensure compatibility with the process. For routine production, it is important to adequately record process details (e.g., time, temperature, equipment used) and to record any changes which have occurred. A maintenance log can be useful in performing failure investigations concerning a specific manufacturing lot. Validation data (along with specific test data) may also determine expected variance in product or equipment characteristics.

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